

methanol system. But unlike the latter system, no further blue-shift occurs when the concentration of water is more than 50%, and no isosbestic points are observed.

Fig. 2. Near infrared spectra of water-acetone mixtures (v/v) at 30°: Water (1) 100, (2) 80, (3), 60, (4) 40, (5) 20, (6) 10, and (7) 0%.

It has been postulated earlier¹⁰ that an association compound between water and acetone is probably present in water-acetone mixtures, since at 2.7 μ the absorption coefficient was several times greater than that of water at 3 μ band. But from Fig. 2 such postulation is difficult. It is rather postulated that if such water-acetone association compound due to interaction between the components, is really present then it is not possible to recognise it by the near-infrared spectra (0.8-1.1 μ), though as mentioned earlier the presence of two isosbestic points in water-methanol systems indicate the interaction between these two components.

Experimental

A Shimadzu 500 spectrophotometer with temperature control was used. Empty quartz cell was used as reference. Path length was 1 cm. Water was triple-distilled. Methanol and acetone were passed through fused CaCl₂ columns and then distilled. Mixtures were made by volume proportions.

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References

1. W. A. P. LUCK in "The Hydrogen Bond", eds. P. SCHUSTER, G. ZUNDEL and C. SANDORFY, North Holland Publishing Co., Amsterdam, 1976, Vol. III, p. 1369.

2. W. A. P. LUCK in "Structure of Water and Aqueous Solutions", ed. W. A. P. LUCK, Verlag Chemie, Weinheim, 1974.
3. R. SUHRMANN and F. BREYER, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1931, 19, 772.
4. E. GANZ *Z. Phys. Chem. B*, 1936, 33, 163.
5. E. GANZ, *Z. Phys. Chem. B*, 1937, 35, 1.
6. R. SUHRMANN and F. BREYER, *Z. Phys. Chem. B*, 1933, 23, 193.
7. H. YAMATERA, B. FITZPATRICK and G. GORDON, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 1964, 14, 268.
8. R. E. VERRALL in "Water—A Comprehensive Treatise", ed. F. FRANKS, Plenum Press, New York, Vol. 3, p. 211.
9. D. WILLIAMS, R. D. WEATHERFORD and E. K. PLYLER, *J. Opt. Soc. Am.*, 1936, 26, 149.
10. D. WILLIAMS and E. K. PLYLER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1936, 4, 154.
11. G. B. M. SUTHERLAND, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1950, 9, 274.
12. R. M. BADGER and S. H. BAUER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, 5, 839.

C.E.C. of Roots of Gram (*Cicer arietinum*) Crop and its Relation to Age and Nutrient Content of Plant

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C. E.C. of roots has an important role in plant nutrition because plants take in their nutrients through roots and if the exchange capacity of roots is high, plants may take more nutrients from the soil. The C.E.C. of the plant roots is highly affected by age of the plant¹⁻⁵. Nutrient concentration of plant at different physiological stages of growth is influenced by the root C.E.C. which has also been expressed by many workers^{2,6,7}. So the present investigation has an important value to study the effect of root C.E.C. on phosphorus, iron and manganese content of different varieties of gram crop at their different physiological growth stages.

Experimental

The experiment was carried out in a net house. Two varieties of gram crop, namely BG-39/2 and BG-231 were sown in fertile alluvial soil (pH, O.C., total N, C : N ratio, C.E.C., available P and total Mn were 6.5, 0.48%, 0.08%, 5.51, 16.90 meq/100 g soil, 2.00 ppm and 33.0 ppm, respectively) taken in a pot without any further addition of nutrients. Plant roots and plant samples were taken at 3 stages, i.e. 30, 45 and 60 days after sowing. The roots were washed in distilled water. After drying, they were milled to pass through 20-mesh sieve and analysed for their C.E.C. by adopting the method of Crooke⁸. It has been reported^{1,9} that keeping

TABLE 1—C.E.C. OF ROOTS (m eq/100 g) AND NUTRIENT CONTENT OF PLANT AT DIFFERENT STAGES OF GROWTH

Growth stage	Root C E C.		P ppm		Fe ppm		Mn ppm	
	BG-39/2	BG-231	BG-39/2	BG-231	BG-29/2	BG-231	BG-29/2	BG-231
Stage-I	21.49	21.00	4333.3	3958.3	910.4	900.1	114.6	100.3
Stage-II	19.66	18.75	4083.3	3666.7	687.5	687.5	80.3	75.0
Stage-III	17.42	16.83	3858.3	3458.0	583.3	572.9	62.3	54.2

the method of determination same. dried roots also show the same C.E.C. as the fresh ones. The plant samples were analysed for P, Fe and Mn by the reported method^{10,11}.

Results and Discussion

The effect of age of plant and nutrient content on C.E.C. of roots are shown in Table 1.

Perusal of Table 1 reveals that varieties of the crop were different in relation to their C.E.C. of roots and in both the cases the root C.E.C. is decreased due to increase in age. Also, the contents of P, Fe and Mn decrease with increase in age, i.e. with decrease in root C.E.C.

The correlation of C.E.C. of roots with age and nutrient content of plants are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—RELATIONSHIPS (r) OF ROOT C.E.C. WITH AGE AND NUTRIENT CONTENT OF PLANTS

	Gram varieties	
	BG-39/2	BG-231
C.E.C. vs age	-0.99 ^a	-0.96 ^a
C.E.C. vs P content	0.75 ^b	0.99 ^a
C.E.C. vs Fe content	0.92 ^b	0.93 ^a
C.E.C. vs Mn content	0.97 ^a	0.86 ^b

^aSignificant at 0.1% level.
^bSignificant at 1% level.

^aSignificant at 5% level.

From data presented in Table 2 a highly significant negative correlation was observed between the C.E.C. of roots and age of the plant. The present study also supports the previous works^{1,2,4,5} on other crops. The decrease in root C.E.C. due to increase in age of plant is due to the variation of composition of cells. It is further revealed that a highly significant positive correlation exists between the C.E.C. of roots and content of phosphorus, iron and manganese. Nutrient content and root C.E.C. of both the varieties are decreased due to increase in age. Similar observations were made on other crops^{3,6}. The increase in nutrient content increases the root C.E.C. by increasing cell division and decreasing the non-pectic carbohydrates in the cell wall of the roots.

References

1. A. K. HELMY and M. M. ELGABALY, *Plant Soil*, 1958, 10, 33.
2. L. C. RAM, *Plant Soil*, 1980, 55, 215.
3. S. SINGH and L. C. RAM, *Plant Soil*, 1978, 49, 661.
4. S. SINGH and L. C. RAM, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1976, 24, 427.
5. S. SINGH and L. C. RAM, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1973, 21, 367.

6. L. SINGH and S. SINGH, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1981, 29, 228.
7. S. G. HEINTZE, *Plant Soil*, 1961, 13, 365.
8. W. M. CROOKE, *Plant Soil*, 1964, 21, 43.
9. R. L. SMITH and A. WALLACE, *Soil Sci.*, 1956, 81, 97.
10. M. L. JACKSON, "Soil Chemical Analysis", Prentice-Hall India Ltd., New Delhi, 1967.
11. C. S. PIPER, "Soil and Plant Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1942.

Magnetic Susceptibility—A Curious Difference in Behaviour Between an Oil and Its Cake

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THE magnetic characteristics of natural products, like oils, nuts, grains etc. have not been reported so far. The main difficulty in using the magnetic data for such materials is their complex composition, unlike simple organic or inorganic materials. Many of the natural products contain water and complex organic molecules which might mask the true magnetic property of the specimen. It might also be expected that the actual magnetic moments of a material, say, an oil would vary from source to source. However, preliminary measurements of magnetic susceptibility with oils indicate a constant value for each oil obtained from different sources. This observation confirmed that magnetic moments could precisely be quoted for these natural products also. In this note we report the data obtained on some vegetable and animal oils, their cakes and seeds.

Experimental

Commercial samples of oils and seeds were used as such. Each material was obtained from five different sources and the quality of each oil was checked by measuring its density and refractive index. These values agreed, within experimental error, with those reported in the literature. Table 1 gives the data available on the chemical composition of oil seeds, oilcakes and oils¹⁻⁴.

The magnetic susceptibility for each sample was measured by the Gouy method⁵. The Gouy balance had a provision for weighing correctly to ± 0.05 mg. The magnetic field strength was measured with